

EBFMC25-OOP-19 · Knowledge and Attitudes Regarding Emergency Contraception Among Family Medicine Residents

 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15830592>

Online Oral Presentation #19 was presented at the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress, held in Ordu, Türkiye, on May 22–24, 2025, and is part of the proceedings titled: *Proceedings of the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress*.

AUTHORS

Bahar Urun Unal
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5433-168X>

Fatma Nur Çakır
<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-3803-5651>

AFFILIATIONS

Selçuk University Faculty of Medicine
Konya, Turkey

Selçuk University Faculty of Medicine
Konya, Turkey

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Emergency contraception is a method used after unprotected or improper use of contraception. Since the use of emergency contraception is not well known by the public, misuse is quite common. It is the duty of family physicians, who are primary care physicians, to provide counseling on this issue. With this study, it was aimed to raise awareness in family physician assistants, to identify deficiencies, and to make them think about attitudes and behaviors with questions. We aimed to contribute to the literature as a guiding study in terms of preventive medicine and family planning.

Materials and Methods: The study was conducted among physicians working as research assistants in the Department of Family Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, Selçuk University in 2025. A total of 103 physicians, 54 women and 49 men, participated in the study. Three different questionnaires, including sociodemographic information form, information research questionnaire, behavior and attitude questionnaire, prepared by the researcher by reviewing the literature, were applied to the physicians. The level of knowledge was scored according to the answers given to the behavior and attitude questionnaire and compared with sociodemographic characteristics. Afterwards, the deficiencies were tried to be eliminated by talking about this issue with the participating research assistants.

Results: The study was completed with a total of 103 participants aged 24-61 years. Of the participants, 52.4% (n=54) were female and 47.6% (n=49) were male. When sociodemographic characteristics and questionnaire total scores were evaluated, the total score of the information research questionnaire was found to be significantly higher in those aged 28 years and above (p=0.022). Those with a shorter residency period had a significantly lower total score on the information research questionnaire (p=0.047). The total score of the behavior and attitude questionnaire was found to be significantly higher in AHU residents (p=0.037).

Conclusion: Emergency contraception is an issue that should be counseled. Family physicians are also in a position to provide counseling on this issue. Family doctors are also in a position to provide counseling on this issue. In the study, it was observed that knowledge, behaviors and attitudes were average and similar in each group.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Emergency contraception, family planning, family medicine residents

INTRODUCTION

Contraception refers to a set of practices in which natural or medical methods are used to intentionally prevent pregnancy. The use of certain sexual behaviors and practices, chemicals, various tools, drugs or surgical applications are included in the scope of contraceptive practices (Jain & Muralidhar, 2011). Emergency contraception is defined as the prevention of unwanted pregnancy before implantation after unprotected sexual intercourse (Tokuc, Eskiocak, & Saltık, 2022). Emergency contraception is also known as morning-after pill

(Derman, 2008). Indications for the use of emergency contraception include forgetting to take regularly used oral contraceptives, unprotected sexual intercourse (miscalculation of the calendar method or failure of the withdrawal method), condom rupture, improper placement, premature removal or rupture of the diaphragm or cervical cap, forgetting to use pills containing only progestin, late injection of injectable contraceptives, dislocation of intrauterine devices, sexual assault (Grimes & Raymond, 2002). The need for hormonal emergency contraception and the research on this subject are quite old. Estrogens were first used as an emergency contraceptive method at high doses in the 1960s (Morris & Van Wagenen, 1966). In the 1970s, Yuzpe et al. started to use a combination of estrogen and progesterone in emergency contraception (Yuzpe et al., 1974; Yuzpe & Lancee, 1977). Intrauterine devices (IUD) were introduced as an emergency contraceptive method in 1976 (Lippes, Malik, & Tatum, 1976). Today, there are mainly two main groups in emergency contraception: Hormonal drugs and IUDs. The drugs can be classified as estrogen and progesterone combinations, progesterone-only drugs and selective progesterone receptor modulators (Mifepristone (Ru-486), Ulipristal Acetate (UPA)). The most commonly used emergency contraceptive methods are oral hormonal drugs because of their ease of use. The most effective method is the copper-containing IUD (Lippes, Malik, & Tatum, 1976).

According to 2008 data, 43.8 million unintended pregnancy terminations were performed worldwide and 49% of these were performed under unhealthy conditions that may lead to maternal morbidity and mortality (Sedgh et al., 2012). According to American data, half of pregnancies are terminated by curettage and 54% of women who undergo curettage become pregnant while using contraceptive methods (Batur, 2012). According to data from the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), 9.7% of women aged 15-44 years use emergency contraceptive methods (Mosher & Jones, 2010). In Turkey, according to the 2018 Turkey Demographic and Health Survey data, the rate of elective abortion among married women aged 15-49 years was found to be 15%. This rate, which is 3 percent in the 15-19 age group, becomes more pronounced in women aged 30 years and older and increases to 27 percent in the 45-49 age group (Hacettepe University Institute of Population Studies, 2018). Considering that the annual pregnancy rate of women in this age group is 10% and half of these are unwanted pregnancies, it is clear that the female population should be educated about contraceptive methods and emergency contraception (Hacettepe University Institute of Population Studies, 2018).

Since the knowledge and practice of emergency contraception is a convenient option to reduce the number of unwanted or unplanned pregnancies, it is important that family physicians, especially those working in primary care, who can provide counseling, have sufficient knowledge on this subject. In this study, we aimed to have information about the level of knowledge and attitudes about emergency contraception among research assistant physicians working in the Department of Family Medicine, to raise awareness on this issue and to develop recommendations for this issue.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The population of this descriptive and cross-sectional study was determined as family physician assistants working at Selçuk University Faculty of Medicine Hospital. The study was completed with 103 participants who volunteered among 113 residents. The data were collected using a questionnaire form consisting of 66 questions prepared by the researchers by reviewing the literature. Statistical analysis of the data obtained in the study was evaluated with the Statistical Packet for The Social Science for Windows Version 22.0 (SPSS) package program at $\alpha=0.05$ level of significance. Descriptive statistics in single groups and Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk analyses were used for continuous data. Chi-Square test was used for categorical data and Independent Group T-Test was used for continuous data in normally distributed groups. Correlation analysis was performed with Spearman Correlation analysis. The study was planned in accordance with the Helsinki Principles and ethics committee approval was obtained from Selçuk University Faculty of Medicine, decision number 2025/79.

RESULTS

The study was completed with a total of 103 participants aged 24-61 years. Of the participants, 52.4% (n=54) were female and 47.6% (n=49) were male. The median age of the participants was 28 (27-33) years. The sociodemographic characteristics of the participants are given in Table 1.

Table 1
Sociodemographic and Clinical Characteristics

		n	%
Gender	Woman	54	52,4
	Male	49	47,6
Age	Median (25-75%)	28 (27-33)	
Marital Status	Married	73	70,9
	Single	30	29,1
Type of Assistantship	AHU	74	71,8
	SAHU	29	28,2
Assistantship Duration	0-18 months	54	52,4
	18-36 months	49	47,6
Year in Business	0-5 years	61	59,2
	5-10 years	24	23,3
	More than 10 years	18	17,5
Number of children	Median (25-75%)	1 (1-2)	
Total		103	100

%. frequency, 25-75%: 1st and 3rd quartile

To measure participants' characteristics about contraception, the following characteristics were assessed: counseling about contraception, sexual intercourse experience, contraception method use, emergency contraception method use, pregnancy while using contraception, preference for emergency contraception method use, and likelihood of misuse (Table 2).

Table 2
Characteristics of Participants About Contraception

		n	%
Counseling about contraception	Yes	39	37,9
	No.	64	62,1
Experience of sexual intercourse	Yes	73	70,9
	No.	30	29,1
Using a method of contraception	Yes	67	65,0
	No.	36	35,0
Using emergency contraception	Yes	31	30,1
	No.	72	69,9
Conception while using contraception	Yes	5	4,9
	No.	98	95,1
Preference to use emergency contraception	Yes	75	72,8
	No.	28	27,2
Possibility of abuse	Yes	84	81,6
	No.	19	18,4
Total		103	100

%. frequency

When sociodemographic characteristics and total scores of the questionnaire were evaluated, the total score of the Information Research Questionnaire of those aged 28 years and above was significantly higher ($p=0.022$). Those with a shorter residency period had a significantly lower total score on the Information Research Questionnaire ($p=0.047$). AHU residents had a significantly higher total score on the Behavior and Attitude Questionnaire ($p=0.037$) (Table 3).

Table 3

Comparison of Sociodemographic Characteristics
and Knowledge Research Questionnaire on Emergency Contraception Methods
and Behavior and Attitude Questionnaire on Emergency Contraception

		BAA Mean±SD	DTA Mean±SD
Gender	Woman	22,8±2,9	56,9±6,9
	Male	22,6±2,5	55,4±9,3
	p*	0,489	0,158
Age	Under 28 years old	22,1±2,9	56,5±7,4
	28 years and older	23,3±2,2	55,8±8,9
	p*	0,022	0,617
Marital Status	Married	22,9±2,6	58,4±7,2
	Single	22,4±2,9	55,2±8,4
	p*	0,245	0,737
Type of Assistantship	AHU	22,7±2,8	56,8±6,9
	SAHU	22,7±2,3	54,6±10,7
	p*	0,247	0,037
Assistantship Duration	0-18 months	22,8±2,2	56,6±7,5
	18-36 months	22,7±3,1	55,7±8,9
	p*	0,047	0,371
Year in Business	0-5 years	22,5±2,8	57,1±6,9
	More than 5 years	23,1±2,4	54,8±9,6
	p*	0,136	0,121
Number of children	There is	22,9±2,7	55,9±8,4
	No	22,2±2,6	57,0±7,2
	p*	0,946	0,557

*: p value was found by Independent Groups T Test, BAA: Knowledge survey questionnaire, DTA: Behavior and attitude questionnaire.

The comparison of the characteristics about contraception with the values of the Knowledge Research Questionnaire on emergency contraception methods and the Behavior and Attitude Questionnaire on emergency contraception is given in Table 4. Accordingly, the total score of the Knowledge Research Questionnaire of those who used emergency contraception method and those who said that there was a possibility of abuse was found to be significantly higher ($p=0.049$ and $p=0.033$).

Table 4

Comparison of Characteristics about Contraception
and Knowledge Research Questionnaire on Emergency Contraception Methods
and Behavior and Attitude Questionnaire on Emergency Contraception

		BAA Mean±SD	DTA Mean±SD
Counseling about contraception	Yes	23,3±2,6	56,1±9,2
	No.	22,4±2,7	56,2±7,5
	p*	0,614	0,551
Sexual intercourse experience	Yes	22,9±2,6	55,3±8,4
	No.	22,2±2,9	58,2±7,2
	p*	0,184	0,699
Using a method of contraception	Yes	22,8±2,6	55,1±8,4
	No.	22,6±2,8	58,1±7,5
	p*	0,315	0,994
Using emergency contraception	Yes	23,0±2,0	58,2±9,4
	No.	22,6±2,9	55,3±7,4
	p*	0,049	0,073
Conception while using contraception	Yes	21,8±1,4	48,8±12,1
	No.	22,8±2,7	56,5±7,8
	p*	0,137	0,295
Preference to use emergency contraception	Yes	22,9±2,5	57,3±8,3
	No.	22,2±3,0	53,2±7,0
	p*	0,338	0,253
Possibility of abuse	Yes	23,0±2,6	55,8±8,0
	No.	21,5±2,6	57,6±8,8
	p*	0,033	0,716

*: p value was found by Independent Groups T Test, BAA: Knowledge survey questionnaire, DTA: Behavior and attitude questionnaire.

When evaluated according to the type of residency, SAHU residents had significantly higher percentages of counseling about contraception, sexual intercourse experience, contraception method use and emergency contraception method use ($p < 0.001$, $p < 0.001$, $p < 0.001$, $p < 0.001$ and $p = 0.041$, respectively) (Table 5).

Table 5

Comparison of Characteristics about Contraception and Type of Assistantship

		AHU n (%)	SAHU n (%)	p*
Counseling about contraception	Yes	14 (18,9)	25 (86,2)	<0,001
	No.	60 (81,1)	4 (13,8)	
Experience of sexual intercourse	Yes	45 (60,8)	28 (96,6)	<0,001
	No.	29 (38,2)	1 (3,4)	
Using a method of contraception	Yes	41 (55,4)	26 (89,7)	<0,001
	No.	33 (44,6)	3 (10,3)	
Using emergency contraception	Yes	18 (24,3)	13 (44,8)	0,041
	No.	56 (75,7)	16 (55,2)	
Conception while using contraception	Yes	3 (4,1)	2 (6,9)	0,546
	No.	71 (95,9)	27 (93,1)	
Preference to use emergency contraception	Yes	51 (68,9)	24 (82,8)	0,156
	No.	23 (31,1)	5 (17,2)	
Possibility of abuse	Yes	59 (79,7)	25 (86,2)	0,446
	No.	15 (20,3)	4 (13,8)	

*: p value was found by Chi-Square Test. AHU: Family Medicine Specialization SAHU: Contracted Family Medicine Specialization.

According to the correlation analysis, there was a high positive correlation between age and number of children ($p < 0.001$). While there was a low-level negative correlation between the total score of the Behavior and Attitude Questionnaire and age and number of children ($p = 0.031$ and $p = 0.010$), there was a low-level positive correlation between the total score of the Information Research Questionnaire ($p = 0.009$) (Table 6).

Table 6

Correlation Analysis between Age, Number of Children, And Knowledge of Emergency Contraception Methods Questionnaire and Behavior and Attitude Questionnaire on Emergency Contraception

		Age	Number of children	BAA	DTA
Age	r	1,000			
	p	.			
Number of children	r	0,710	1,000		
	p	<0,001	.		
BAA	r	0,123	0,106	1,000	
	p	0,218	0,285	.	
DTA	r	-0,213	-0,252	0,255	1,000
	p	0,031	0,010	0,009	.

p value was calculated according to spearman correlation analysis. BAA: Knowledge exploration questionnaire, DTA: Behavior and attitude questionnaire.

DISCUSSION

Unintended pregnancies, which are very common in our society, are an important women's and public health problem that can be prevented with appropriate, timely and appropriate interventions. The most effective solution to prevent these pregnancies in primary care is the regular and conscious use of family planning (FP) methods. However, in some cases, especially after unprotected sexual intercourse, emergency contraception (EC) may become the only solution. Unfortunately, there is a lack of knowledge and misconceptions both in the community and among health care providers. Healthcare personnel who lack knowledge about EC, the fact that EC is not offered as a routine counseling service in FP outpatient clinics, couples' low level of knowledge about EC, and false beliefs prevalent in the society severely limit the effective and widespread use of EC methods (Aksu & Karaöz, 2008; Bilgili & Ayaz, 2009; Li et al., 2014). This situation was also clearly demonstrated in our study. While 65% of family medicine residents were generally aware of contraception

methods, only 30.1% used EC methods and 37.9% provided counseling. These rates were similarly observed in studies conducted in different provinces. In a study conducted in Ankara in 2024, it was reported that knowledge scores changed significantly according to education ($p<0.05$), in Denizli in 2022, the rate of hearing about EC was 64% and the rate of use was 18.3%, and in studies conducted in Zonguldak in 2018 and Kahramanmaraş in 2019, it was reported that the level of knowledge increased significantly as the grade level and age increased (Altaş Baştuğ, 2024; Bayındır, 2022; Uğur, 2018; Dalkıran, 2019).

In this study, we evaluated the knowledge and attitudes of family medicine residents towards emergency contraception (EC). While 65.3% of the participants had used a method of contraception before, only 30.1% had used emergency contraception. The rate of counseling was 37.9%. These findings show that despite the theoretical knowledge, implementation in practice remains limited. Similarly, in the study of Arıöz Düzgün et al. (2023), it was reported that 65.1% of women had insufficient knowledge about EC and that the level of knowledge was significantly associated with the level of education ($p<0.05$) (Arıöz, Şahin, Güler, & Ünsal, 2023). In the study conducted by Koçak et al. (2016) reported that 74.9% of women had heard of EC, 39.1% had used this method at least once, and 78.6% had used it two or more times (Yüksel Koçak et al., 2016). In the same study, it was reported that there was a significant relationship between the level of knowledge and the level of education ($p=0.001$), which overlaps with the statistically significant difference ($p<0.05$) observed between age and duration of residency and knowledge level in our study (Yüksel Koçak et al., 2016). In the study conducted by Aşut et al. (2019) in Northern Cyprus, only 33.9% of medical faculty students knew the correct time of effective use of EC and 57.6% could correctly define it (Aşut et al., 2019). EC use among the sexually active was reported as 23.1%. These rates are similar to the rate of 30.1% among resident physicians in our study. In the study conducted at Gümüşhane University, 42.3% of the university students stated that they had knowledge about FH; however, it was determined that the knowledge level of these students about hormonal FH methods and postcoital IUD applications was quite limited. A significant difference was found between education level and knowledge level ($p<0.05$) (Can Gürkan, Şimşek Şahin, & Bozkurt, 2022).

In a 2003 study in India, 85% of health workers were aware of CoA, but only a small proportion had the correct dose and timing (Tripathi, Rathore, & Sachdeva, 2003). In a 2003-2004 study in Nigeria, 87% had heard of CoA, but only 10% had accurate knowledge, and the misconception that CoA has an abortion effect was over 30% (Ebuehi, Ebuehi, & Inem, 2006). In a 2012 study in Iran, only 35% of participants had "good" knowledge (Mohammad-Alizadeh-Charandabi, Farshbaf-Khalili, & Moeinpoor, 2012). In a 2011 study at Edinboro University, 74% of students had heard of EC, 17% had used it, and only 16% knew that the university health center offered EC (Miller, 2011).

These studies reveal that although awareness of EC is widespread in different countries, the depth of knowledge and correct implementation remain limited. The common trend is that there is a gap between knowledge and practice, and the most significant variables that increase the level of knowledge are age, educational level and professional experience. In conclusion, more content should be added to both the medical education curriculum and in-service training programs to improve the knowledge and attitudes of family medicine residents on FH, and their consultancy experience in clinical practice should be increased. Structured, interactive and case-based trainings may be effective especially for young and continuing health professionals.

CONCLUSION

In this study, the knowledge, attitudes and behaviors of healthcare workers about emergency contraception were evaluated. The median age of the participants was 28 years and the proportion of women was 52.4%. Those aged 28 years and older and SAHU residents had significantly higher knowledge scores. Knowledge level was lower in those with a shorter residency period. The knowledge scores of those who used emergency contraception and those who thought that there was a possibility of misuse were also high. In addition, SAHU residents were found to be more active in terms of counseling about contraception and method use. There were strong associations between age and number of children and weak associations between knowledge and attitude scores and age. These findings suggest that young and inexperienced health workers need more training and guidance on contraception. Emergency contraception is an issue that requires counseling and family physicians are in a position to provide counseling on this issue. It is seen that conducting such studies in larger groups will increase awareness and complete the missing information.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

REFERENCES

- Aksu, H., & Karaöz, B. (2008). The need for promotion of emergency contraception methods. *Journal of Health Sciences*, 17, 63–68.
- Altaş Baştuğ, Ö. (2024). *Evaluation of the knowledge and behaviors of women applying to Ankara Training and Research Hospital family medicine outpatient clinics about emergency contraception* [Medical specialty thesis, T.C. University of Health Sciences].
- Arıöz, A., Şahin, S., Güler, D., & Ünsal, A. (2023). Women's knowledge level of emergency contraception, some related factors and its relationship with health literacy. *Turkish Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*, 17(4), 529–533.
- Aşut, Ö., Yılmaz, B., Kaya, Z. Y., & Demir, T. (2019). Knowledge and attitudes of medical students about emergency contraception. *Cukurova Medical Journal*, 44(2), 612–620. <https://doi.org/10.17826/cumj.473959>
- Batur, P. (2012). Emergency contraception: Separating fact from fiction. *Cleveland Clinic Journal of Medicine*, 79(11), 771–776. <https://doi.org/10.3949/ccjm.79a.12019>
- Bayındır, S. (2022). *Knowledge levels and behaviors of married women aged 15–49 years who applied to Pamukkale University Hospital Family Medicine Polyclinic about emergency contraception methods* [Medical specialty thesis, Pamukkale University].
- Bilgili, N., & Ayaz, S. (2009). Emergency contraception: Knowledge and experiences of women. *TAF Preventive Medicine Bulletin*, 8, 251–258.
- Can Gürkan, Ö., Şimşek Şahin, E., & Bozkurt, F. (2022). University students' knowledge of emergency contraceptive methods and usage rules. *Gümüşhane University Journal of Health Sciences*, 11(2), 415–424. <https://doi.org/10.37989/gumussagbil.888078>
- Dalkıran, Y. (2019). *Knowledge levels and behaviors of students studying in Kahramanmaraş Sütçü İmam University Faculty of Medicine and Faculty of Health Sciences about sexual health, reproductive health and emergency contraception* [Medical specialty thesis, Kahramanmaraş Sütçü İmam University].
- Derman, O. (2008). *Preventive health services in adolescents*. https://www.sabem.saglik.gov.tr/Akademik_Metinler/goto.aspx?id=1455
- Ebuehi, O. M., Ebuehi, O. A., & Inem, V. (2006). Health care providers' knowledge of, attitudes toward and provision of emergency contraceptives in Lagos, Nigeria. *International Family Planning Perspectives*, 32(2), 89–93. <https://doi.org/10.1363/3208906>
- Grimes, D. A., & Raymond, E. G. (2002). Emergency contraception. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 137(3), 180–189. <https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-137-3-200208060-00010>
- Hacettepe University Institute of Population Studies. (2018). *Turkey Demographic and Health Survey 2018*. Hacettepe University, Ministry of Health, SPO and TÜBİTAK.
- Jain, R., & Muralidhar, S. (2011). Contraceptive methods: Needs, options and utilization. *Journal of Obstetrics and Gynaecology of India*, 61(6), 626–634. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13224-011-0107-7>

- Li, H. W. R., Lo, S. S. T., & Ho, P. C. (2014). Emergency contraception. *Best Practice & Research Clinical Obstetrics and Gynaecology*, 28, 835–844.
- Lippes, J., Malik, T., & Tatum, H. J. (1976). The postcoital copper-T. *Advances in Planned Parenthood*, 11(1), 24–29.
- Miller, L. M. (2011). College student knowledge and attitudes toward emergency contraception. *Contraception*, 83(1), 68–73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.contraception.2010.06.005>
- Mohammad-Alizadeh-Charandabi, S., Farshbaf-Khalili, A., & Moeinpoor, R. (2012). Emergency contraception: Providers' knowledge and attitudes and their relationship with users' knowledge and attitudes at public health centers/posts of Tabriz. *Journal of Caring Sciences*, 1(1), 53–59. <https://doi.org/10.5681/jcs.2012.008>
- Morris, J. M., & Van Wagenen, G. (1966). Compounds interfering with ovum implantation and development: 3. The role of estrogens. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 96(6), 804–815. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0002-9378\(66\)90676-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0002-9378(66)90676-4)
- Mosher, W. D., & Jones, J. (2010). *Use of contraception in the United States: 1982–2008* (Vital and Health Statistics Series 23, No. 29). National Center for Health Statistics.
- Sedgh, G., Singh, S., Shah, I. H., Ahman, E., Henshaw, S. K., & Bankole, A. (2012). Induced abortion: Incidence and trends worldwide from 1995 to 2008. *The Lancet*, 379(9816), 625–632. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(11\)61786-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(11)61786-8)
- Tokuc, B., Eskiocak, M., & Saltık, A. (2022). Emergency contraception. *Journal of Continuing Medical Education*, 11(3), 94–97.
- Tripathi, R., Rathore, A. M., & Sachdeva, J. (2003). Emergency contraception: Knowledge, attitude, and practices among health care providers in North India. *The Journal of Obstetrics and Gynaecology Research*, 29(3), 142–146. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1341-8076.2003.00090.x>
- Uğur, H. (2018). *Evaluation of medical faculty students' knowledge, attitudes and behaviors about emergency contraception* [Medical specialty thesis, Zonguldak Bülent Ecevit University].
- Yuzpe, A. A., & Lancee, W. J. (1977). Ethinylestradiol and dl-norgestrel as a postcoital contraceptive. *Fertility and Sterility*, 28(9), 932–936.
- Yuzpe, A. A., Thurlow, H. J., Ramzy, I., & Leyshon, J. I. (1974). Post coital contraception: A pilot study. *Journal of Reproductive Medicine*, 13(2), 53–58.
- Yüksel Koçak, D., Büyükkayacı Duman, N., Topuz, Ş., Yılmazel, G., Güngör, T., & Başçı, A. B. (2016). Knowledge, attitudes and behaviors of women of reproductive age about emergency contraception. *Journal of Gynecology Obstetrics and Neonatology*, 13(3), 112–116.

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

Bahar Urun Unal
Selçuk University Faculty of Medicine
Konya, Turkey
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5433-168X>
urunbahar@gmail.com